

The Effectiveness of a Developed Instructional Unit in Vocational Education Curriculum Based on International Standards in Nutrition and Sports in Improving Attitudes Towards Practicing Sports Activities Among Eighth Grade Female Students in Jordan

Reem Suleiman Ahmed "Ali Saleh", Tarik Faris Al-Soub

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 13, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Instructional Unit (study unit), Vocational Education, International Standards, Nutrition and Sport, Attitudes towards practicing Sport Activity, primary Eighth Grade</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5098186</p>	<p><i>Objective: identifying the effectiveness of a developed Instructional Unit in Vocational Education Curriculum based on International Standards in Nutrition and Sports in improving attitudes towards practicing sports activities among eighth grade female students in Jordan.</i></p> <p><i>Design: The study followed the quasi-experimental approach designed by the experimental and control groups.</i></p> <p><i>Setting: Female students of the eighth grade of basic education in private schools in Jordan.</i></p> <p><i>Participants: students were selected from the eighth-grade students in Amman. Two divisions was randomly assigned to be an experimental group of (26) and the other to be a control group of (29) students.</i></p> <p><i>Intervention: ten week (2h/wk) the researcher led program held in schools in Amman during school.</i></p> <p><i>Main Outcome Measure: improving female student's attitudes towards practicing sports activities in Jordan. Knowledge about Vocational Education Curriculum.</i></p> <p><i>Analysis: Changes from beginning to end of program were analysed with paired covariance (ANCOVA) was performed.</i></p> <p><i>Results: The results showed a statistically significant effect on the developed unit based on the international standards in the level of attitudes towards sports activities.</i></p> <p><i>Conclusion and Implementation: Developing an Instructional Unit in Vocational Education Curriculum, based on International Standards of Nutrition and Sports, may be improving attitudes towards practicing sports activities.</i></p>

Introduction

Health education is considered to be one of the most important key points of the vocational education study as stated in the general framework document and the general and specific outputs of the vocational education study for the basic education stage in Jordan ⁽¹⁾.

The comprehensive health education in the school is characterized by its reliance on planned, sequenced, developmentally appropriate, culturally inclusive experiences based on the relevant health behavior theories, and a focus on the emotional, intellectual, physical, and social dimensions of health, care must therefore be taken to expose students to diverse educational techniques, and evaluate their achievement through a variety of evaluation strategies ⁽²⁾.

There are many global experiences in promoting comprehensive health education. The Singaporean Ministry of Health noticed the benefits of a comprehensive curriculum. Consequently, it established the health-promoting school model. It was efforts to improve school health called Championing Efforts Resulting in Improved School Health. It aims to encourage Primary and Secondary Schools to develop comprehensive programs to promote school health ⁽³⁾.

School health education (Health education with an emphasis on diet and sport activity) aims to help students to develop the knowledge and skills necessary to make correct decisions, practice healthy behaviors and create appropriate conditions for health.

Health education can be applied in schools in several different ways depending on the country's needs and available resources. It can be taught as a specific topic, or as part of other subjects, such as; Science, Home Economics, Mathematics, and Agriculture, or ideally as a combination of the two ⁽⁴⁾.

Educational institutions face multiple and accelerating challenges, as a result of the dramatic changes in knowledge, information, technology and communication systems. In addition to the growing system's role based on culture and free economy, which makes there an urgent need for standards to work through to ensure the

achievement of the elements of competition, quality and excellence ⁽⁵⁾. This requires a comprehensive review of the education system as one of the determinants of any country's productivity and as one of the factors of societal progress and development, and the axis of national security for society. Therefore, all countries were keen to define the inputs and outputs of the educational process to raise its developmental returns and enable society to achieve higher rates of development, progress and competitiveness ⁽⁶⁾.

International Standards are characterized by their ability to various changes in the educational system. Therefore, they are considered as engines by which to judge its quality because it enables us to assess the information quality that the student possesses, and provides us with the necessary tests to know the extent of the progress made by our educational system compared to the global system ⁽⁷⁾. It also justifies the tests that can be taken by the official and local school, workers and societies, and helps in establishing the nature of appropriate curricula, the necessary evaluation programs, and provides support and training for distinguished teachers ⁽⁸⁾.

Attention to global standards in nutrition and sport activity for the individual is considered the mainstay for creating a healthy generation free from food diseases capable of understanding and production. Also knowledge of international standards in nutrition and sport is one of the factors that shall be taken care of, they believe that food plays an important role in the nations and people's lives, as the nutritional state is a mirror in which the image of human progress is reflected in its various stages, and that attention to nutrition and sport reduces the chance of an individual being exposed to malnutrition ⁽⁹⁾.

⁽¹⁰⁾ Emphasized the possibility of including and integrating nutrition education in the school curricula. One of its most important goals was for teachers to learn ways to integrate nutrition education into their current lesson plans in various studies, as science is a great topic to integrate nutrition into, because of the chemical reactions that occur during the cultivation and the growth of our food, as well as the interactions that occur between food and our bodies ⁽¹¹⁾. Nutrition can also be incorporated into mathematics by using mathematical equations to calculate the necessary calories and the amount of food from each food group, as well as the cooking period, all of these skills, are essential to obtain food. Also, students can learn correct reading and correct spelling in the English language subject while they learn the concepts of nutrition at the same time. Students can also learn nutrition in social studies where students present a project through which they know the history of different foods, their origins and cultures, or students can research the ingredients for traditional recipes and their nutrients and how the need for nutrients has evolved ⁽¹²⁾.

Based on this, the Food and Nutrition Council of America indicated the need to pay attention to nutrition and sports and to develop strategies that achieve a balance between them, like the fact that food science studies nutrients and the role of their component elements in preserving the organism life ⁽¹³⁾. It is a group of integrated processes carried out by cells, tissues, and systems where the body acquires energy and nutrients to carry out its normal functions through the nutrients consumed and the body's ability to convert materials needed for metabolism and metabolic ⁽¹⁴⁾.

By learning about the Educational Literature, it was noted that International Standards in the field of nutrition and sport activity in the Ministry of Education in California, most states of America and the World Health Organization, focus on the following topics: Nutrients, Food Groups, Ideal Mass and Breakfast Importance, System of Alternatives, and Diet Food, methods of preserving and storing food, diseases of malnutrition and some chronic and common diseases and their relationship to food and nutrition, as well as focus on the importance of sports activity and the dangers resulting from the lack of sport activity and identify inexpensive options available at home, school and fitness centers for practicing sport activity, as well as these global standards focused on the impact of the family, culture, media and peers on nutrition and sporting activity, and the way to access trustworthy information about nutrition and sporting activity, setting goals, and making decisions about them ⁽¹⁵⁾. These global standards focused on interpersonal communication and the practice of behavior that promotes healthy physical health ⁽¹⁶⁾.

Sports activity is one of the necessary means to build an individual's personality and raise him in an integrative education by exploiting many of his natural motives. As the activity that is practiced regularly according to foundations and rules contributes to developing the students' knowledge side and changing a lot of the information, concepts, attitudes and motivations they have. ⁽¹⁷⁾

Attitudes are considered one of the most important determinants of human behavior. The attitude is defined as a state of nervous and psychological preparedness or preparedness organized by the individual's experience. It determines how they respond to groups, things, topics, attitudes or symbols ⁽¹⁸⁾. also attitudes reflect a set of beliefs, feelings, and behaviors related to each other that are organized around a specific thing or situation that may be positive or negative, and the attitudes determine how individuals behave towards others and events; thus, feelings become behaviors and choices are a powerful behavior indicator, which in turn can be dynamic, constructive, learned, modified, or even alternative behavior ⁽¹⁹⁾.

METHODS

Study Design

To determine the effectiveness of the module developed in the vocational education curriculum based on the international standards in nutrition and sports in improving attitudes towards practicing sport activity, the study used the semi-experimental method to examine the effectiveness of the independent variable (the developed unit) in the dependent variable (attitudes towards practicing sport activity). The used design was the design of the experimental and the control groups by pre and post measurement.

Participants and Recruitment

Al-Jami'a Secondary Schools for girls was chosen purposely because the school's administrative and teaching bodies showed their cooperation. Two divisions were selected from the eighth grade divisions and were randomly distributed, so that one of them represented an experimental group of 26 students and the other represented a control group of 29 students.

Intervention:

The two researchers prepared and developed the study unit within the following steps:

To achieve the objectives of the study, and based on the educational literature, the study unit in Nutrition and Sports was developed with the aim of providing: Special products in accordance with international standards in nutrition and sport, which are proposed to be included in the books of professional education for the eighth grade in Jordan and to examine their effectiveness in improving attitudes towards the practice of sports activity among female students, As these outputs included the cognitive, skill and emotional aspects, and the study unit was built in the form of classes and its number (20) teaching sessions using an investigation method to achieve special products in accordance with international standards in nutrition and sports that are suitable for students of the eighth grade at this stage of life. By making use of the theoretical framework and what it contains of: specialized scientific resources, previous studies, and the outlines of the curriculum for health and professional studies for the eighth grade basic, and being guided by the views of a number of specialists in the curricula, and in the nutritional and health field, as well as many references and research, Arab and foreign conferences and seminars, and international standards, Among them are: Health education content standards for school students in America in the states (New Jersey, Texas, and California). The list consisted in its initial form of (8) main criteria in nutrition and sport activity, which are: (basic concepts, analysis of effects, access to valid and applicable information, communication between individuals, decision-making, setting goals, practicing health-promoting behaviors, health promotion). In addition, special productions of the developed unit were formulated and derived, and there were (36) special products that were distributed on the unit's topics, which numbered (4) topics, and on the teaching classes, which reached (20) teaching sessions. The content was also organized in the form of bulletins at the end of each session in line with international standards in nutrition and sport, as the teaching methods in the unit were developed in an investigative manner, in order to achieve the results according to international standards. A daily plan has been developed to implement each class within the unit. Table (1) shows the title of the topic, the order of the topic, and the number of classes.

Table (1) Title of the topic, the order of the topic, and the number of lessons for the developed study unit entitled B (Nutrition and Sports)

Title of the topic	Thread arrangement	number of classes
Food and nutrition	1	6
My body is a mirror of my health	2	4
sport activities	3	6
The body needs energy	4	4

Instruments, Measurer, Procedures and Data Analysis

For the purposes of this study, the researchers used a study tool aims to measure attitudes towards practicing sport activity from the viewpoint of female eighth-grade students. The researchers took several steps in developing the scale, viewing of a set of foreign studies on attitudes towards sport activity, where the tools of these studies were used in formulating the scale paragraphs, interpreting and classifying the paragraphs, selecting the paragraphs that fit the objectives of this study, and formulating them in an appropriate manner. As the scale was in its initial form (34) paragraphs to be in its final form (27) paragraphs. The researchers chose that the answer to the scale paragraphs be of five degrees, and accordingly, the minimum score that the student can obtain on the scale is (27) degrees, and the maximum score is (135) degrees.

The current level of performance on the attitudes towards practicing sport activity among female students in the eighth grade was divided into three levels: (high, medium, and low) by dividing the range of numbers from 1 to 5 into three categories to obtain the extent of each level, i.e. 1.33. So, the levels are as follows: Low level (1 - less than 2.33), medium level (2.34-3.67), and high level (more than 3.68-5).

The Validity of the scale of attitudes towards practicing sport activity :

The validity of the scale was verified by face validity and content validity: the validity of the attitudes towards practicing sport activity was verified by presenting the scale to (14) specialized arbitrators in the field of educational psychology, measurement, evaluation, curriculum, and teaching in the Jordanian universities, as well as some specialists working in the field as shown in Appendix No. (1). In light of the arbitrators' observations, the authors rephrased some of the statements and excluded some ambiguities. The arbitrators expressed their suggestions regarding the nature, language, and appropriateness of the paragraphs. Accordingly, the number of paragraphs has been reduced to (27) instead of (34) paragraphs.

Stability of the Scale of Attitudes towards practicing sport activity:

The researchers measured the stability of the scale of attitudes towards practicing sport activity in two ways:

- **Method of Test-re-test** by applying it to an exploratory sample of (20) students out of the study's sample with a time difference of two weeks. The coefficient of stability was calculated using correlation coefficient Pearson. The stability coefficient of the scale as a whole (0.98) was appropriate for the study, because many researchers consider that the stability factor that exceeds (0.8) guarantees the propensity for the stability of the tool used in this type of stability, and also compared to the stability results of other studies for the same scale.
- **Kronbach Alfa Method:** The stability was calculated by applying it to an exploratory sample of (20) students from the study community and out of its sample, by the Kronbach AlfaMethod, where its value was (0.88) for the scale paragraphs, and this value is good compared to the results of the stability of many studies for the same scale, such where the value of the Kronbach stability coefficient alpha of the attitudes towards practicing sport activity scale was (0.71), which indicates that the stability is good for the paragraphs of the attitudes towards practicing sport activity in the current study, and thus the scale and its paragraphs are valid for application.

Results and Discussion

Demographics:

Results related to the study question, which states: "Is there a statistically significant difference at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the attitudes towards practicing sport activity in the experimental and control samples attributed to the effectiveness of (developed study unit based on international standards in nutrition and sports, the assessed unit)?"

To answer the study question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the pre and post measurement of the eighth-grade students in Al-Jami'a Secondary Schools were calculated on the attitudes scale for the experimental and control groups, and it was as shown in Table (2).

Table (2)

The arithmetical averages and standard deviations of the responses of the eighth-grade students on the scale of the attitudes towards practicing sport activity of the experimental and control groups

Group	Numbers	Pre-measure		Post-measure	
		Arithmetic Means	Standard Deviations	Arithmetic Means	Standard Deviations
Experimental	26	3.61	.29	4.36	.395
Control	29	3.66	.35	3.47	.368

Table (2) shows that there is an apparent difference between the experimental and control groups in the two arithmetic averages and the two standard deviations on the attitudes towards practicing sport activity scale in the pre and post-measurement, with the mean of the calculation for the experimental group on the scale of attitudes towards practicing post-sport activity was (4.36) with a standard deviation of (.395), while the arithmetic mean of the control group on the same scale was (3.47) with standard deviation (.368). To verify that this difference in the two averages between the experimental group and the control group has statistical significance at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), an analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was performed; Table (3) shows that.

Table (3)

Analysis of the common variation to indicate the differences in the attitudes towards practicing sport activity in the pre and post-measurement between the control and experimental groups

Source	Total Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Average Squares	F	Significance	ETA Box
Pre-Measurement	.200	1	.20	1.38	.24	.025
The Group	10.92	1	10.92	75.48	.00	.59
The Error	7.52	52	.14			
Total Summation	18.47	54				

The results in Table (3) indicate that there is a statistically significant difference between the experimental and control groups in scores on the attitudes towards practicing sport activity scale. Where the

value of (F) (75.48) in terms of statistical significance of (.00), which is a statistically significant value at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

To determine the size of the effect of the study unit variable "Effect size" on the attitudes towards practicing sport activity, the Eta square was used in light of the level of statistical significance. The results in Table (3) show that the effect size was good (0.59). This indicates that (0.59) of the variance is attributed to the effectiveness of the upgraded study unit in improving attitudes towards practicing sport activity of the experimental group.

In order to determine the difference in the results of the eighth-grade female students on the attitudes towards practicing sport activity scale, the two modified post-arithmetic averages and the two standard errors of the performance of the eighth-grade primary students on the scale were extracted, and the results showed in Table (4).

Table (4)

Modified arithmetical averages and standard errors of the responses of the eighth-grade female students on the attitudes towards practicing sport activity scale

The group	Modified post-arithmetic mean	Standard error
Experimental	4.36	.07
Control	3.47	.07

Table (4) shows that the difference was in favor of the experimental group, as the adjusted arithmetic mean of the experimental group reached (4.36) with a standard error (0.07), while the adjusted arithmetic mean of the control group reached (3.47) with a standard error (0.07). Through this result, shows that the developed study unit based on international standards of nutrition and sports, the assessed unit, which was applied to female students of the eighth grade in the Al-Jami'a Secondary Schools - girls - Amman, it was effective in improving attitudes towards practicing sport activity among the experimental group students.

Discuss the results related to the study question

These results are inferred from the impact of the developed study unit based on international standards in improving attitudes toward practicing sport activity, as evidenced by the difference in the dimensional scale between the average performance of the experimental group of (4.36) and the average performance of the control group of (3.36). The reason for this may be attributed to the enhanced results of the attitudes towards practice sport activity in the unit, which are based on international standards in nutrition and sports, on which the students were trained by the teacher, which led to an improvement in their attitudes towards practicing sport activity. It is evident that the attitudes towards practicing sport activity can be learned and acquired by female students if they are provided with the outcomes, health and scientific content, methods and good methods of education that keep pace with modern developments and developments and are based on international standards.

The reason for this may be attributed to the fact that the personality of the eighth grade student at this critical age stage has approached full maturity to realize the importance and value of sports activity in terms of health, social and psychological, and in their acquisition of physical fitness and a better physical image, and the prevention of obesity, this is what the developed unit dealt with in its outcomes and activities in the subject of sporting activity, for this critical age stage.

The reason for the effectiveness of the improved study unit may be due to the creation of a comfortable classroom environment in which the students felt free to express their ideas without fear, which allowed them to interact positively with each other, build bridges of trust, form positive social relationships, cooperate, discuss, follow instructions and commit to attending classroom classes. All this was reflected on the performance of the experimental group sample and led to the development of attitudes towards practicing sport activity.

The results of improving the students' attitudes toward practicing sport activity among the experimental group sample may also be attributed to educating the students about the factors affecting the formation of positive attitudes towards sport activity, including: the practicing of parents and comrades for sport activity, and encouraging the means of propaganda and the media to do them.

The study found an effect of the positive attitudes of the study sample on the practice of sports and physical activities to a high degree, as the results showed that there are a set of variables that have an impact on the positive attitudes of practicing sports activities, including: Parents and comrades previous practice of sports activities, and propaganda means and the media.

IMPLICATIONS FOR RESEARCH AND PRACTICE

It may be possible to increase the attitudes towards practicing sport activity for female students in general and the eighth grade in particular, and through the application of the study tool related to the scale of attitudes towards practicing sport activity, it becomes clear that the students responded positively to its paragraphs, which reflects the importance of developing a study unit in vocational education and measuring its impact on the attitudes of female students, which is reflected in its impact on students in every school grade.

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Recommendations:

the study recommends the following:

1. Conduct training courses for vocational education teachers to familiarize them with the importance of international standards in nutrition and sport in improving attitudes towards practicing sport activity.
2. Develop vocational education curricula to be based on international standards because of their importance in developing the emotional aspects of female students, as many field studies, including the current study, it showed that there is a positive and beneficial effect of these developed study units on female students in different academic stages,
3. Provide officials in the Ministry of Education with the results of the study; to be able to identify the most important attitudes towards practicing sport activity among female students in the eighth grade, and to use the study unit and apply it by professional education teachers in the elementary stage in general and the eighth grade in particular, and to circulate it to public schools.

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Author Information

Dr. Reem Suleiman Ahmed "Ali Saleh"

Aqaba University of Technology

Dr. Tarik Faris Al-Soub

Assistant Professor/ Aqaba University of Technology
